

Infected panicles after artificial inoculation with *Acrocyndrium oryzae* in Thailand.

Repl-ication	Infected panicles (%)		
	Spray suspension of spores	Injection suspension of spores	Check
1	80.9	78.1	0
2	73.3	69.7	0
3	72.4	77.8	0
4	65.9	77.3	0
Av.	73.1	75.7	0

The young panicles remained within the sheath, whose upper surface was entirely covered with dark-brown lesions.

We found that typical symptoms appeared after artificial inoculation by both spray and injection with a suspension of the fungus *Acrocyndrium oryzae* in the booting stage (see table). The experiment was conducted in nylon screen cages; insecticides were applied to eliminate mites or insects. The results indicate that the primary factor in rice abortion or sheath rot in Thailand is the fungus *Acrocyndrium oryzae*. The dispersion and severity of the disease may be related to the biological relationships between the sheath rot fungus and mites, the fungus and stem borers, or both.

Research on the ecology and natural enemies of the rice stem borer *Diopsis thoracica* in Malawi

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Diopsis thoracica flies spend the dry season in shady places along banks of streams, where they can be found in large swarms. In December, at the beginning of the rainy season, they move back to the rice fields. They lay eggs singly on rice stems or leaves, the highest numbers at about 25 days after transplanting. The larva enters the stem via the leaf sheath and develops there. The feeding larva causes yellowing of the terminal leaf (deadheart). Its occasional attack on older rice can cause whiteheads. Except when it attacks seedlings, the larva remains on the same stem until pupation; but just before pupation it may move to another stem or even another hill.

The eggs take an average of 3 days to hatch. The larval stage lasts approximately 38 days and the pupal stage 14 days. There is one main generation each rainy season and one partial second generation in later planted fields. In the dry season (Apr.–Nov.) the number of flies and the number of eggs laid in fields with a second crop are low.

Egg parasitoids seem to be the most important natural control against *D. thoracica*. Three species have been found: two species of the genus *Trichogramma*, which are presently being described; and *Trichogrammatoidea simmondsi*, which is less important. All 3 egg parasitoids were found to be susceptible to organophosphorous insecticides and chlorinated hydrocarbons. Application of phosphamidon in nurseries brought egg parasitism down to below 2%. Predation of eggs by small Carabid beetles and mites could reach 30%.

Up to 25% of the pupae were attacked by the parasitoid *Aprostocetus* sp. Adult flies were parasitized by six species of fungal pathogens. Crab spiders and Odonata were recorded as predators of the fly.

The effect of *D. thoracica* on transplanted rice is difficult to assess.

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Occurrence of the rice tarsonemid mite at IRRI

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A phytophagous tarsonemid mite was found infesting rice plants on the IRRI farm. The mite, identified as *Stenotarsonemus spinki* by Dr. Robert L. Smiley of the US Department of Agriculture, lives in colonies within the intercellular air space of the upper part of leaf sheaths and, occasionally, in the basal part of the midrib of leaf blades. It causes necrotic streaks in the interveinal epidermis (see photo).

When a female mite is artificially inoculated into the intercellular air space of a leaf sheath, it becomes gravid and, in 2 days, begins to lay eggs randomly at the rate of about 15/day over a period of 5 or more days. The eggs are opaque, ovoid, and large (125 × 80 microns) in comparison with the size of the adult. They hatch into 6-legged larvae in 2 to 4 days. The newly emerged larvae are opaque-white, about 140 microns long, and rather inactive. After feeding, they grow to about 300 microns long, and their wrinkled integument smoothens as the cuticle becomes tightly stretched. Then the larvae enter a quiescent stage.

The average duration of the active larval stage is 1 day and that of the quiescent stage, 2 days. The life cycle is

Necrotic streaks caused by the Tarsonemid mite on rice leaf sheaths.

completed in 6 days. The adults are slightly tanned, and about 245 microns long. The females at the preovipositional stage are far more active than the males, and are mainly responsible for dispersal. The males are often observed carrying quiescent larvae on their backs. The species is facultatively parthenogenetic; the virgin females lay only a few eggs, which produce only males.